

Angle of Arrival-based Beam Selection for Hybrid Beamforming with Machine and Deep Learning

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Abstract—This paper investigates how angle-of-arrival (AoA) information can be exploited by deep-/machine-learning approaches to perform beam selection in the uplink of a mmWave communication system. Specifically, we consider a hybrid beamforming setup comprising an analog beamforming (ABF) network followed by a zero-forcing baseband processing block. The goal is to select the optimal configuration for the ABF network based on the estimated AoAs of the various user equipments. To that aim, we consider (i) two supervised machine-learning approaches: k-nearest neighbors (kNN) and support vector classifiers (SVC); and (ii) a feed-forward deep neural network: the multilayer perceptron (MLP). Computer simulations reveal that, for a specifically-designed codebook of analog beamformers, this task can be effectively accomplished by such data-driven schemes. Performance, in terms of classification accuracy and sum-rate, is very close to that achievable via exhaustive search.

I. INTRODUCTION

Machine learning (ML) techniques have been known for a long time as powerful tools for classification and regression (prediction) problems. More recently, deep learning (DL) has emerged with more advanced tools capable of building universal classifiers and/or approximate general functions. Typical problems/scenarios where machine learning methods have been successfully applied include, but are not limited to, image restoration and identification, natural language processing, network security, customer segmentation, predictive maintenance (e.g. for machinery in industrial plants), etc.

To date, the application of ML/DL techniques to communication problems has been mostly in the field of wireless *network optimization* [1]. Authors have tackled a number of problems like intelligent resource management, cell association, selection of radio access technologies, or spectrum management, to name a few. In contrast, there has been very limited progress towards the use of ML/DL techniques for problems and functionalities related with the physical layer (PHY) of communication systems (e.g., coding, modulation, detection, equalization, pre-coding, among others). However, it is generally agreed that enhancing (or even replacing) some PHY functionalities with ML and DL approaches could help achieve the stringent requirements associated with the future releases of 5G [2]. For this reason, some authors [3] have started investigating how autoencoders can be used to

model an end-to-end communication system comprising the encoding, channel and decoding blocks, for MIMO point-to-point and interference channels. The adoption of feedforward deep neural networks for joint channel estimation and data detection under an MMSE criterion is addressed in [4]. Other research works include the adoption of convolutional neural networks (CNN) to carry out sensing, compression and recovery of channel state information (CSI) in the feedback channel of massive MIMO systems [5]; the use of support vector classifiers (SVC) to perform antenna [6] or beam selection [7], or the exploitation of CNNs for modulation classification tasks [3].

The shift towards communications in mmWave bands makes it feasible to implement transceivers with many more antenna elements. In order to keep hardware cost and computational complexity at reasonable levels, a number of techniques have been proposed. Hybrid beamforming, for instance, can be used to partition beamforming into the digital and analog (RF) domains and, by doing so, reduce the number of RF chains needed in the base station. In this context, the development of efficient (analog) beam selection techniques has become a hot research area. In [8], for instance, the authors present an iterative scheme where, in each iteration, the beam that contributes less to the sum-rate of a multi-user MIMO system with a discrete lens array and zero-forcing digital precoding block is eliminated. In [9], instead, the proposed low-complexity beam selection algorithm exploits the fact that an approximation of the sum-rate can be computed out of the elements of the effective channel matrix at the output of the analog beamforming (ABF) block. The approximation is near optimal in the high-SNR regime. A different approach is adopted in [10], where beam selection is accomplished with a bio-inspired ant colony optimization algorithm of a very reduced complexity. The applicability of ML techniques to beam selection tasks is investigated in [7]. Specifically, the authors model beam selection (in a hybrid receiver architecture with a ZF block) as an instance of a multi-class classification problem, and attempt to solve it with a support vector classifier (SVC). To that aim, the availability of the actual angle-of-arrival (AoA) and amplitude information for each scattering path is assumed. Complementarily, in [11] Heath *et al* investigate the performance of several ML schemes (SVC, Adaboost, Decision trees, Random forests) but also deep neural networks

(DNN) and reinforcement learning for beam pair selection in vehicle-to-infrastructure settings. The proposed method leverages on positioning information (vehicle locations) which is assumed to be supplied by an external entity and be error-free.

Transmit *antenna selection* (TAS) is also an effective way of lowering the number of RF chains needed. In [6], the authors propose to solve the combinatorial TAS problem with ML techniques: support vector classifier or k -Nearest Neighbors (kNN) [12]. Interestingly, their symbol error rate performance is acceptable when compared with the benchmark, an optimization-based technique based on singular-value decomposition, at a much lower complexity. Complementarily, [13] focuses on MIMO wiretap channels and resorts to SVM and Naive Bayes classifiers as a means to maximize the secrecy performance. Finally, the authors of [14] adopt a multi-armed bandit framework (reinforcement learning) to maximize throughput in MIMO point-to-point channels via antenna subset selection.

In this paper, we investigate the exploitation of angle-of-arrival (AoA) information by a number of deep-/machine-learning approaches to perform analog beam selection in the uplink of a multi-user MIMO mmWave communication system. As in [7], [8], [10], we adopt a hybrid beamforming architecture with an analog beamforming (ABF) network and a ZF baseband processing block. Unlike [7], [11], here AoA (and received power) information is not assumed to be known or externally supplied. Instead, it is estimated by the same system via a Capon (minimum variance) spectral estimator [15]. And the impact of such estimates on performance is also carefully analyzed. To perform beam selection, we resort to a number of ML/DL approaches this including support vector classifiers (like in [7], [11]) but also consider other schemes like k -nearest neighbors (that was used in [6] for transmit antenna selection) and the multi-layer perceptron (MLP). Unlike in many previous works, we propose to use a codebook of analog beamformers with adjustable beamwidth (rather than phased-arrays or DFT-based codebooks) as a means to enhance/guarantee system performance. As benchmarks, we consider a scheme where the optimal beam is identified via exhaustive search, and random beam selection.

II. SIGNAL AND SYSTEM MODEL

Consider the uplink of a multi-user SIMO system operating in the mmW-Wave band. As shown in Fig. 1, the base station (BS) is equipped with N_{BS} antennas and serves K mobile terminals (or user equipments, UE). The BS adopts a hybrid beamforming architecture, comprising an analog beamforming (ABF) and a digital/baseband (BBF) beamforming block. The former performs a spatial pre-filtering of the received signal, whereas the latter is aimed at removing inter-user interference. The ABF network provides full connectivity among the set of receive antennas and the N_{RF} radiofrequency chains. Hereinafter, we assume that the number of active users does not exceed the number of available RF chains, i.e., $K \leq N_{RF}$. The

Fig. 1: System Model.

received signal at the BS after RF and baseband combining can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{W}^H \mathbf{B}^H \mathbf{H} \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{W}^H \mathbf{B}^H \mathbf{n} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{BS} \times K}$ is the channel matrix, $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times 1}$ denotes the transmit signal, with its elements fulfilling $\mathbb{E}[\|x_k\|^2] = P^t$ for $k = 1 \dots K$; vector $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{BS} \times 1}$ is zero-mean i.i.d. AWGN noise with variance σ^2 , i.e., $\mathbf{n} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \sigma^2 \mathbf{I}_{N_{BS}})$; and, finally, $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{RF} \times K}$ and $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{BS} \times N_{RF}}$ stand for the BBF and ABF matrices, respectively. For the channel, we adopt a geometric model with L scattering paths, which is widely-used in mm-Wave communications. Consequently, for the channel matrix $\mathbf{H} = [\mathbf{h}_1 \dots \mathbf{h}_K]$, we have that

$$\mathbf{h}_k = \sqrt{\frac{1}{L\rho_k}} \sum_{i=1}^L \alpha_{k,i} \mathbf{a}_{BS}(\theta_{k,i}^{BS}), \quad (2)$$

where $\alpha_{k,i}$ is the complex gain of the i -th path with $\mathbb{E}[\|\alpha_{k,i}\|] = 1$, ρ_k is the path-loss between the BS and the k -th user, and $\theta_{k,i}^{BS} \in [-\pi/2, \dots, \pi/2]$ denotes the AoA of the i -th path of user k . Vector $\mathbf{a}_{BS}(\theta_{k,i}^{BS})$ is the antenna array response at the BS. Hereinafter, we assume uniform linear arrays (ULA) and, hence, it can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{a}_{BS}(\theta_{k,i}^{BS}) = \left[1, e^{j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} d \sin(\theta_{k,i}^{BS})}, \dots, e^{j(N_{BS}-1)\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} d \sin(\theta_{k,i}^{BS})} \right] \quad (3)$$

where λ is the signal wavelength, and d is the distance between antenna elements (in the sequel, we assume $d = 0.5\lambda$). Note that, for large L , the channel model turns out to be Rayleigh fading.

III. ANALOG AND DIGITAL BEAMFORMING STRATEGIES

The proposed hybrid beamforming architecture for the BS comprises an analog and baseband (digital) beamforming blocks that are described in this section.

A. Analog Beamforming (ABF)

There exists a pre-defined codebook \mathcal{B} of $B = |\mathcal{B}|$ different configurations of the ABF network (referred to, in the sequel, as *analog beamformers*) that reads

$$\mathcal{B} = \{\mathbf{B}_1, \dots, \mathbf{B}_{|\mathcal{B}|}\} \quad (4)$$

with $\mathbf{B}_i \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{BS} \times N_{RF}}$ denoting each of those analog beams. Since we are interested in performing a spatial pre-filtering, we let the j -th column vector $\mathbf{b}_{i,j}$ in $\mathbf{B}_i = [\mathbf{b}_{i,1}, \dots, \mathbf{b}_{i,N_{RF}}]$ point at a different direction θ_d out of a set of D AoAs evenly spaced in $[-\pi/2 \dots \pi/2]$. And, as a design decision, we set D in such a way that the resulting number of elements (analog beamformers) in the codebook $B = \binom{D}{N_{RF}}$ is larger than or equal to N_{BS} .

A straightforward choice for $\mathbf{b}_{i,j} = \mathbf{b}_{i,j}(\theta_d)$ would be phased arrays, namely,

$$\mathbf{s}(\theta_d) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_{BS}}} \left[1, e^{j\frac{\pi}{\sin(\theta_d)}}, \dots, e^{j(N_{BS}-1)\pi \sin(\theta_d)} \right] \quad (5)$$

For large N_{BS} , however, the resulting beams become too narrow (to recall, their 3 dB beamwidth is $2/N_{BS}$). As discussed in Section IV ahead, this yields a poor classification performance and, thus, must be avoided. Instead, we let \mathbf{b} (sub-indices i, j have been dropped, for brevity) be the solution to the following optimization problem:

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{\mathbf{b}}{\text{maximize}} && \int_{\theta_d - \frac{\Delta\theta}{2}}^{\theta_d + \frac{\Delta\theta}{2}} \mathbf{b}^H \mathbf{s}(\theta) \mathbf{s}^H(\theta) \mathbf{b} \, d\theta \\ & \text{subject to} && \|\mathbf{b}\|^2 = 1. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $\frac{\Delta\theta}{2}$ is a design parameter related with the interval around θ_d where we want to *broaden* the beam. The score function in (6) can be re-written as $\mathbf{b}^H \mathbf{C} \mathbf{b}$ where we have defined:

$$\mathbf{C} = \int_{\theta_d - \frac{\Delta\theta}{2}}^{\theta_d + \frac{\Delta\theta}{2}} \mathbf{s}(\theta) \mathbf{s}^H(\theta) \, d\theta. \quad (7)$$

The (n, m) element in \mathbf{C} thus reads

$$[\mathbf{C}]_{n,m} = \Delta\theta e^{j\pi(n-m)\theta_d} \text{sinc}\left((n-m) \frac{\Delta\theta}{2}\right) \quad (8)$$

with $\text{sinc}(x) = \frac{\sin(\pi x)}{\pi x}$.

From all the above, one concludes that \mathbf{b} is given by the eigenvector associated with the largest eigenvalue of matrix \mathbf{C}^1 . Figure 2 below depicts the periodogram of the set of analog beamformers in a codebook designed according to (6).

B. Baseband Beamforming (BBF)

For baseband beamforming, we adopt a zero-forcing ZF scheme, as e.g., in [7]. By defining the effective channel matrix as the product of the actual channel and the analog beamforming matrix, namely, $\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}} = \mathbf{B}^H \mathbf{H}$, we have

$$\mathbf{W} = (\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}}^H \mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}})^{-1} \mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}}^H. \quad (9)$$

¹Clearly, the absolute value of each element in \mathbf{B}_i is not necessarily 1. This means that the ABF network can no longer be realized through a set of phase shifters. Instead, each phase shifter must be accompanied by an amplitude control device. Yet this increases the overall cost of the ABF network, for a reduced number of amplitude levels, the cost can be affordable. And, in any case, substantially lower than that of using digital beamforming for the whole set of N_{BS} antennas.

Fig. 2: Periodograms of the elements in the ABF codebook ($B = 10$, $N_{BS} = 10$, $N_{RF} = 3$, $\Delta\theta = 3/N_{BS}$, $D = 5$).

IV. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Our goal is to select the analog beamformer from the B -element codebook \mathcal{B} such that the sum rate at the output of the BBF block is maximized. From the system model presented in the preceding section, the sum rate can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} R(b) &= \sum_{k=1}^K \log_2(1 + \gamma_k(b)) \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^K \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{P^u / \rho_k}{\sigma^2 \left[(\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}}(b)^H \mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}}(b))^{-1} \right]_{kk}} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where $[\mathbf{A}]_{kk}$ denotes the k -th element in the diagonal of matrix \mathbf{A} , and where the dependency of \mathbf{H}_{eff} on the codebook index b has been made explicit.

In order to select the optimal beamformer (and avoiding exhaustive searches over the codebook elements), one needs to leverage on \mathbf{H} as channel state information (CSI). However, under the assumption of a hybrid beamforming architecture, \mathbf{H} cannot be readily estimated in the digital domain (since the number of RF chains, N_{RF} , is smaller than the number of antennas, N_{BS}). Alternatively, we propose to use some sufficient statistic derived from \mathbf{H} . In particular, we investigate whether the AoA and received power for each user terminal can be exploited. The rationale behind can be found in Fig. 3 which depicts which is the optimal analog beamformer (found via exhaustive search) for each tuple of AoAs for the $K = 2$ user case. Interestingly, analog beamformers are clustered into several regions. Hence, the selection process can be modeled as a classification problem that, in turn, can be effectively solved with machine and deep learning tools (see Section V ahead). To stress, the appearance of the scatter plot above these lines critically depends on the choice of the pre-defined set of analog beamformers (see discussions in the preceding section). For instance, a codebook built on phased arrays (i.e., $\Delta\theta = 0$) would, to a large extent, decouple such dependency on AoA information. This stems from the fact that, for very narrow beams, multiple non adjacent beamformers still yield high sum rates. And, hence, the clustering of beamformers into disjoint decision regions vanishes. This is why, in Section

Fig. 3: Actual decision regions with identical received powers ($B = 10$, $N_{BS} = 10$, $N_{RF} = 3$, $K = 2$, $N_{\text{train}} = 3000$, $\text{SNR} = 20\text{dB}$).

III-A, we designed an ad-hoc codebook of beamformers with larger beamwidths.

A. AoA and Received Power Estimation

By resorting to the Capon (i.e., minimum variance) power spectral estimator [15], we can effectively estimate the set of AoAs and received powers. To that aim, we use the $N_{RF} \times 1$ baseband signal $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{B}^H \mathbf{H} \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{B}^H \mathbf{n}$, that is, a *filtered* version of the received signal *after* ABF and analog to digital conversion (to recall, the received signal itself lies in the RF domain). Hence, the power spectral density reads

$$\mathbf{P}_b(\theta) = \frac{1}{\mathbf{s}^H(\theta) \mathbf{B}_b (\mathbf{R}_{yy})^{-1} \mathbf{B}_b^H \mathbf{s}(\theta)} \quad (11)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\mathbf{s}^H(\theta) \mathbf{B}_b (\mathbf{B}_b^H \mathbf{R}_{rr} \mathbf{B}_b)^{-1} \mathbf{B}_b^H \mathbf{s}(\theta)} \quad (12)$$

with \mathbf{R}_{yy} and \mathbf{R}_{rr} standing for the covariance matrices of the filtered and received signals, respectively. It is worth noting that a *directional* analog beamformer, such as those designed in Section III-A, might cancel out (part of or all) the received signals. To avoid that, a set of non-directional beamformers \mathbf{B}_b must be used for AoA estimation. Specifically, we let $\mathbf{B}_b = \mathbf{Q} (\mathbf{Q}^H \mathbf{Q})^{\frac{1}{2}}$, where \mathbf{Q} is a $N_{BS} \times N_{RF}$ matrix of complex-valued random i.i.d. Gaussian entries. Figure 4 depicts the power spectral densities that can be obtained with the periodogram and Capon methods. The power spectral density obtained with the Capon method applied to the received signal is used as a benchmark. On the one hand, the spatial resolution of the Capon method is unsurprisingly higher than that of the periodogram. And, on the other, the impact of using a filtered version of the signal is quite limited: the power spectral density is a bit noisier but, still, the resolution and peaks in the spectral density barely change.

Fig. 4: Power spectral densities for the periodogram and the Capon method with the received and filtered signals (non-directional random analog beamformers). Green markers denote the actual AoAs ($B = 15$, $N_{BS} = 15$, $N_{RF} = 4$, $K = 2$, $\text{SNR} = 20\text{dB}$).

V. DATA-DRIVEN ANALOG BEAM SELECTION

The task of selecting the optimal analog beamformer can be modeled as a supervised learning problem. Specifically it can be cast into a multi-class classification task where:

- The input is given by the set of (estimated) AoAs and received powers for all active users, namely, $\mathbf{t} = [\theta_1, \dots, \theta_K, P_1^r, \dots, P_K^r]$. The number of active users K is assumed to be known.
- The output is an index to the element (beamformer) in the codebook, $b \in [1, \dots, B]$, yielding the highest sum rate after ZF.

The next subsections describe (i) the training set to be used; and (ii) the machine and deep learning schemes considered in this work.

A. Training set description

The training set comprises a total of M examples \mathbf{t}_m stacked in a training matrix $\mathbf{T} = [\mathbf{t}_1^T, \dots, \mathbf{t}_M^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times 2K}$ and a class label vector $\mathbf{c} = [c_1, \dots, c_M]^T \in \mathbb{N}^{M \times 1}$ with the corresponding outputs. The generation of the training set consists in the following steps:

- 1) Generation the received signal for a total of M realizations of the communication scenario (user locations, transmit powers, path-loss).
- 2) Collection /estimation of the AoA and receive power information as per Section IV-A.
- 3) Performing ABF and BBF on the received signal for each example with all the possible analog beamformers in the codebook, as in (1).
- 4) Computation of the corresponding sum rates as per (11);
- 5) Letting the label of each example be the index of the analog beamformer yielding the highest sum rate, i.e., $c_m \in \{1, 2, \dots, B\}$.

To avoid significant bias in the training, features are normalized prior to their use by the learning schemes, namely, $t_{ij} \leftarrow (t_{ij} - E_i t_{ij}) / (\max_i [t_{ij}] - \min_i [t_{ij}])$

B. Machine Learning Schemes

The so-called k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN) scheme is one of the simplest ML-based classification methods. For a new example \mathbf{t} , the kNN classifier finds the k nearest² entries in the training set \mathbf{T} . Then kNN declares the class label for the new example \mathbf{t} based on a (possibly weighted) majority of the nearest neighbors' labels. The only hyper-parameter of the algorithm is G , the number of nearest neighbors to find. Typically, G is set to be an odd number, to avoid ambiguity.

We will also consider a Support Vector Classifier (SVC). For a multi-class classification problems (like ours), SVCs need to solve B binary classification problems. Each of them, identifies one category vs. the other categories (i.e. one-vs.-rest approach). Specifically, during the training phase, binary SVCs fit a separating hyperplane with optimal geometric margin (i.e. maximum distance to the closest elements in each of the two classes). Next, in the test phase, those hyperplanes are used to decide in which region (i.e., class, beamformer index) the new example \mathbf{t} lies³. Since our problem is not linearly separable (see Fig. 3), we introduce a Gaussian (radial-based) kernel function to transform the input data. This allows to transform hyperplanes into more general boundaries. For this kernel in particular, the hyperparameters here are σ_k , the variance of the Gaussian kernel; and, C , a penalty parameter aimed to balance bias and overfitting (see [12] for details).

C. Deep Learning Scheme

Fig. 5: Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP), a feedforward deep neural network.

Feedforward deep neural networks (DNN) like the multi-layer perceptron (MLP) can be regarded as universal function approximators. As shown in Fig. 5, our L -layer MLP consists of: one input layer with $2K$ elements (AoAs, received powers), one output layer with B neurons (the number of

elements in the codebook), and $L - 2$ hidden layers with N_l ; $l = 2, \dots, L - 1$ neurons each. This MLP defines a mapping $f(\mathbf{t}, \Phi) : \mathbb{R}^{2K} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^B$ of an input vector \mathbf{t} onto an output vector \mathbf{r}_L through L iterative processing steps:

$$\mathbf{r}_l = f_l(\mathbf{r}_{l-1}; \phi_l); \quad l = 1 \dots L \quad (13)$$

where $f_l(\mathbf{r}_{l-1}, \phi_l) : \mathbb{R}^{N_{l-1}} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{N_l}$ is the mapping associated to the l -th layer. Such mapping depends, on the one hand, on the output from the previous layer and, on the other, on the parameter set of that layer, ϕ_l , with $\Phi = [\phi_1, \dots, \phi_L]$ denoting the set of all parameters in the model (see below for details). The l -th layer is said to be *dense* if $f_l(\mathbf{r}_{l-1}; \phi_l)$ is of the form

$$f_l(\mathbf{r}_{l-1}; \phi_l) = \sigma(\mathbf{W}_l \mathbf{r}_{l-1} + \mathbf{b}) \quad (14)$$

with $\mathbf{W}_l \in \mathbb{R}^{N_l \times N_{l-1}}$ and $\mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_l}$ denoting a matrix of weights and a bias vector, respectively; and $\sigma(\cdot)$ is a (typically non-linear) activation function. In this work, Rectified Linear Units (ReLU) are used as activation functions in all hidden layers. On the contrary, a Softmax activation function is used at the output layer, so that the probability for each beamformer can be effectively computed. Further, each hidden layer is followed by a dropout layer in order to avoid overfitting when using the training set. In the training phase, the parameter set in each layer, i.e., $\phi_l = [\mathbf{W}_l, \mathbf{b}_l]$, is adjusted via the so-called stochastic adaptive gradient descent algorithm (Adagrad, [16]) and backpropagation [12]. The goal is to minimize the categorical cross entropy (i.e., maximize classification accuracy).

VI. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In this section, we assess the performance of the proposed ML- and DL- beam selection schemes. Unless otherwise stated, the system scenario comprises one BS equipped with $N_{BS} = 16$ receive antennas and $N_{RF} = 6$ RF chains; and a total of $K = 4$ active users. We consider uplink channels with a single scattering path (i.e., $L = 1$), same transmit power $P_k = P$ for all k and (possibly) different path-losses for the various users.

For the implementation, training and evaluation of the proposed schemes, we resorted to the Scikit-learn [17] and Tensorflow [18] libraries, for ML (kNN, SVC) and DL (MLP) ones, respectively. Besides, we also used Keras [19], which runs on top of TensorFlow (and also other DL libraries like Theano or CNTK) and provides a high-level neural network API (Application Programming Interface) to it. The number of examples in the training and test sets was set to $M = 3000$ and $M_{\text{test}} = 3000$, respectively. The hyper-parameters in each model were optimized via grid search: $G = [3, 5, 10, 20, 50, 80, 100, 200]$, $\sigma_k^{-1} = [10^{-4}, 10^{-3}, 0.01, 0.1, 0.2, 0.5, 1, 5]$, and $C = [1, 10, 100, 1000, 2000, 5000]$. A different model was fit for each SNR. As for the MLP, the number of layers and neurons in the hidden layers was $L = 5$ and $N_l = 125$, respectively. During training, the dropout rate was set to 20% which sufficed to prevent overfitting. All the aforementioned parameters were optimized manually.

²In this work, we restrict ourselves to the most popular distance measure: the Euclidean distance, namely, $d(\mathbf{t}_m, \mathbf{t}) = \|\mathbf{t}_m - \mathbf{t}\|^2$

³If binary SVCs predict multiple labels, the one with the highest confidence score is finally selected.

Fig. 6: Decision regions for the kNN scheme. Circles with two colors indicate classification errors. Received powers are identical for both users ($B = 10$, $N_{BS} = 10$, $N_{RF} = 3$, $K = 2$, $M = 3000$, $\text{SNR} = 20\text{dB}$)

Results are given in terms of classification accuracy and sum-rate (see next subsections). As benchmarks, we include (i) a *random* beam selection (uniform distribution in $\{1, \dots, B\}$); and (ii) an *optimal* beam selection, which is accomplished via exhaustive search.

A. Classification Performance

Here, we investigate the classification accuracy. First, we focus on the decision regions generated by the kNN scheme (Fig. 6). Clearly, the regions are very similar to the actual ones, which are displayed in Fig.3 since the classification accuracy for this toy example was 85%. Circles with two different colors indicate classification errors (the inner circle is associated to the optimal beam selection decision). Interestingly, most of the errors occur between adjacent regions (e.g. red-yellow, yellow-orange); and, also, the scatterplot is symmetrical with respect to the secondary diagonal since an exchange of AoA among the two active users yields exactly the same solution (beamformer). Similar results were obtained with the SVC and MLP schemes. Next, we turn our attention to the impact of the receive SNR at the RF antennas on classification accuracy (Fig. 7). The two upper plots illustrate the performance with the *actual* AoAs and received powers, in order to isolate the impact of CSI estimation. Several comments are in line. First, that classification accuracy clearly depends on algorithmic complexity: MLP outperforms SVC, and SVC outperforms kNN. For identical receive powers (top, left), the performance loss with respect to the optimal classifier is comparable for the three approaches and in the range of 20% to 30%. Still, their performance is radically higher than that of random beam selection (classification accuracy of $1/B$, where B is the cardinality of the codebook). In the presence of fluctuations in the received power of ± 2 dB (e.g., due to imperfect power control and/or different user-to-BS distances), the classification

Fig. 7: Classification accuracy with (i) actual (top) and estimated (bottom) AoAs and receive powers; and (ii) identical (left) or different (right) receive powers ($N_{BS} = 16$, $N_{RF} = 6$, $K = 5$, $M = 3000$, $M_{\text{test}} = 3000$).

accuracy exhibits some degradation (top, right). This holds, in particular, for the ML approaches. Apparently, the more complex map of decision regions that such fluctuations entail are better handled by the MLP since, in general, DNNs turn out to be more sophisticated classifiers than *classical* ML ones. Besides, the impact of the SNR on performance is negligible. Apparently, the fact that ML/DL models are trained for specific SNRs largely mitigates such impact.

However, performance is notably different with *estimated* AoAs and received powers (via Capon power spectra). Even with identical received powers (bottom, left), the classification accuracy substantially degrades: from 70% – 80% to 30% – 40%. The main reason for that is two-fold. First of all, we have the limited angular resolution of the Capon estimator that, in addition, must operate with a filtered version of the received signal (see Section IV-A). In other words, when the AoAs of two users are too close, they are merged together which implies that (i) their received powers are added up; and (ii) the second AoA (and received power) is attributed to any of the *noisy* spectrum peaks shown in Fig. 4. When this occurs, the resulting AoA/received power tuples can be quite different and, thus, the probability of selecting a beamformer which is radically different from the optimal one increases too. Besides, even if users continue to be separable in the angular domain, the additive noise has a direct impact on the quality of AoA and received power estimates. Hence, and unlike the case with actual CSI (top row), classification accuracy improves when SNR increases. Finally, now we observe that MLP experiences difficulties in handling the combined effects of CSI estimation *and* received signal fluctuations (bottom, right): its performance is now comparable to that of kNN and SVC.

Fig. 8: Sum rates with (i) actual (top) and estimated (bottom) AoAs; and (ii) estimated AoAs; and (ii) identical (left) or different (right) receive powers ($N_{BS} = 16$, $N_{RF} = 6$, $K = 5$, $M = 3000$, $M_{test} = 3000$).

B. Sum Rate Performance

Yet classification accuracy is a relevant performance measure, from a communications point of view we are more interested in sum rate measures. This is illustrated in Fig. 8. Here, we observe that relatively poor classification accuracy yields in some cases acceptable sum-rates. Interestingly, for the scenario with identical received powers (left column), classification accuracies of 80% render sum rates virtually identical to that of optimal beam selection. As discussed earlier, this is due to the fact that most classification errors occur among adjacent regions. These regions, by codebook construction (see Section III-A) are often associated to beamformers with a similar angular response. And, for a given set of AoAs, they result into similar sum-rates. Only when classification accuracy severely degrades due to CSI estimation and/or fluctuations in the received power, does the sum-rate degradation of MLP, kNN and SVC wrt the optimal approach become noticeable (bottom plots). This holds in particular when *both* effects simultaneously occur (bottom, right) and, in particular, for the high SNR regime. Still, in all *complex* scenarios with power fluctuations and/or estimated CSI, the DL approach (MLP) outperforms and is more robust than its ML counterparts (kNN, SVC). Of course, this comes at a price of a higher computational complexity of the classification tool. A more detailed analysis of complexity is left for subsequent works.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have investigated how angle-of-arrival information can be exploited by deep-/machine-learning approaches to perform beam selection in a hybrid beamforming setup. Specifically, we have posed the beam selection task as a multi-class classification problem and solved it via two machine-learning (ML) approaches: k-nearest neighbors, support vector classifiers; and one deep learning approach:

the multilayer perceptron). We have also designed a new beamformer set with larger and configurable beamwidth which is tailored to the beam selection task. Computer simulation results reveal that classification accuracy exhibits some degradation in the presence of received power fluctuations which is larger for ML approaches (actual CSI). With estimated CSI, the degradation is more severe, both for ML and DL schemes. This is mostly due to the limited spatial resolution of the Capon-based AoA estimation block operating on a filtered received signal, and the impact of additive noise on CSI estimates (yet the impact of the latter is moderate). In general, MLP outperforms both kNN and SVC methods in terms of classification accuracy. However, ML and DL approaches with moderate classification performance still exhibit a sum-rate performance which is close to the optimal one. This follows from the fact that most classification errors occur among adjacent regions. Only when classification accuracy severely degrades due to CSI estimation and/or fluctuations in the received power, the sum-rate degradation becomes noticeable, in particular, for the high-SNR regime.

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